

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN LESSONS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the effectiveness of interactive simulators and their use in mathematics lessons in elementary school.

INTRODUCTION

The use of different models in the teaching and learning process is not a new method. Nowadays, model modeling is of great importance in education. There are various virtual laboratories, interactive simulators and the possibility of using them. One of these sites was created by PhET Technology Physical Education, Nobel Prize winner in natural sciences K. Wiman. The PhET website has a variety of themes, many of which are created in Java and Macromedia Flash. There are also options for mobile devices right now.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interactive PhET simulators can be used in almost all aspects of the educational process: from primary school to higher education. In recent years, even in the field of medicine, simulators have been used.

Within the framework of the Information Laboratory of Virtual Education, studying new areas of learning using educational modeling will increase students' self-esteem and their ability to perceive world events, their ability to independently analyze problems that arise throughout life, and their readiness to apply the acquired knowledge is formed. Tamki, and the virtual laborer, which are reacting to the student, is to the state of virtue of the UC of the Use of the Encouraging Outhenication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the main reasons for using simulators is that they are a very cheap alternative to real objects. Some research may pose a threat to human life, for example, nuclear physics. This research not only requires significant financial costs, but also poses a threat to the lives of researchers. The interactive simulators presented in the program are presented not only in English. You can find translations of up to 80 languages, in particular 14 models in Uzbek.

PhET simulators are a very flexible software package that can be used in many areas. PhET simulators can be used to learn and apply interactive methods for integrating integrated education into primary education [2].

Nowadays, it is impossible to imagine human life without technology. Nowadays, concepts such as an application, the Internet, and the use of mobile devices are not new to anyone. The telephone, computer and the like have come to us to such an extent that it has a significant impact on the learning process. Educational institutions in the country are equipped with stage-by-stage technical means (TV, projector, computer, electronic scoreboard, ...) and the Internet. Proper and appropriate use of such tools will have a positive impact on the quality of education. In particular, the ability of an older student to distinguish from hearing is well developed. Practice plays an important role among students of this era. Most teachers use traditional teaching methods in the process of teaching subjects. Along with traditional teaching methods, organizing classes using innovative teaching methods is one of the most important tasks facing a modern teacher. The Internet and its limitless possibilities can be used to accomplish these tasks. Thus, it is effective to use interactive simulators with innovative significance in primary education. Below are some software options.

Software Arithmetic_en. This program gives you instructions on replication, sharing, and related topics such as finding an unknown multiplier. These programs, by enabling students to clearly understand the above concepts framed in the student's mind and strengthen their knowledge, will increase the student's interest in the subject [3].

The program consists of divisions Multiply (Factor), Divide (Divide), each section is divided into 3 levels, with the ability to know: Level 1 (Level 1), Level 2 (level 2), level 3 (3 degrees). At each level, tasks are given in grades 1–6, levels 1–9 and levels 1–12 in level 2.

Multiply and Divide find the reader or multiplier. When a multiplier is found, it is automatically installed by the application instead of tables. By eliciting and strengthening their knowledge through game programs, rather than asking students to perform oral sex, they increase the reader's interest in learning.

As you know, the new curriculum for primary school education is the second class "Shares, geometric shapes and sizes", "Percentage of number, percentage of number in words or numbers", "Search for numbers by parts and parts" and "Comparison of parts". Typically, these topics are explained to students by folding or cutting pens into squares, circles, and cuts. The textbook also contains a description of the rectangle, circle, cross section and tasks on the subject.

Using Build-a-fraction_ru, fraction-equality_ru, fraction-intro_en eliminates the above problems. Firstly, it saves the teacher's time, and secondly, it will be economical. The most important thing is that the program has many types of figures and is easy to follow. Therefore, the student has a clear idea of the subject. Generally speaking, classes organized using interactive PhET simulators in primary education are very effective compared to conventional ones [4].

CONCLUSION

It is well known that theory has practically no practice, and practice is theoretically unthinkable. In order for the knowledge that we give in the mind of the student to be fully preserved, they must have a clear understanding of this knowledge. The above-mentioned

programs serve as a useful tool for teaching methodological assistance to the teacher to have quick and easy access to teaching effectiveness.

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